

Questionnaires for personal settings

1. What is your name?
2. What are your hobbies?
3. What is on your bucket list?
4. How do you spend your free time?
5. Have you ever met a celebrity? Which celebrity would you like to meet?
6. Describe yourself in three words.
7. What is your favorite color?
8. What is your favorite animal?
9. Do you work better in the morning or at night?
10. Do you play any sports?
11. How good is the college campus according to you?

Questionnaires for professional settings

1. Actor: "Good morning, do you have an appointment booked already, or are you here to register?"
2. ~~Alright, I see you're token number is 7~~
3. What are your symptoms?
4. How long have you been experiencing?
5. You're booked with **Dr. Sharma**. Have you visited him before?"
6. Your slot is at 11:45 AM. Do you think you'll be able to stay until then?"
7. ~~Alright, I see you're token number is 7 and is scheduled on August 26~~
8. Your room number will be **203 in block B**
9. Actually, the doctor is running late, so your appointment will be at **12:45 PM** instead of 11:45. Will that work for you?
10. The consultation fee is **₹559**. Will you be paying by cash or card?"
11. ~~We also provide a 30% discount if you take a membership. Would you be interested? (391.3)~~
12. We usually close the clinic at **1 PM**. Since your appointment is at 12:45 PM, do you think you'll have enough time?
13. ~~You should bring your aadhaar.~~
14. If you're running late, just call us. Would you like me to note that down for you?
15. If you miss your slot, you'll have to wait until 6:30 PM. What would you prefer—be on time, or wait?"

Filler Questions:

1. "Have you filled out the new patient forms online, or would you like to do that here?"

2. *Ask details, like address, name and so on*
3. *"Is this your first time visiting our clinic?"*
4. *"How did you hear about Dr. Sharma?"*
5. *"Do you have any insurance information we should add to your file?"*
6. *"Are you comfortable waiting in the main waiting area, or would you prefer a more private space?"*
7. *"Is there anything else you'd like to mention about your symptoms?"*
8. *"Do you have any questions for us before you see the doctor?"*
9. *"Would you like a glass of water while you wait?"*
10. *"Just to confirm, is this the best number to reach you on today?"*
11. *"Have you had any previous consultations for these symptoms?"*

